

LIVING HERITAGE & LIVING LABS

Post-Conference Recommendations for the Preservation
and Development of Living Cultural Heritage

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Guidance Brief

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- ✓ Living heritage & community participation
- ✓ Heritage living labs
- ✓ Ethics, rights & consent
- ✓ Responsible openness & digital sustainability
- ✓ Education, co-creation & governance

Living Heritage, Living Labs Guidance Brief

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Living heritage remains alive when it is continuously practised, reinterpreted, and transmitted across generations in meaningful social contexts. This Post-Conference Guidance Brief synthesises the main outcomes of the international network conference Living Heritage: Knowledge, Identity, Practice (2025) and offers actionable recommendations for applying living-lab methodology in cultural heritage.

Heritage living labs are participatory, real-world environments where communities, practitioners, researchers, and institutions co-create, test, and refine approaches to safeguarding and sustainable development of living cultural heritage. They respond to pressing challenges highlighted at the conference: rapid social change, climate and mobility pressures, digital transformation and digital fragility, and persistent gaps between research, conservation practice, and community realities. The brief defines heritage living labs, outlines their core functions and minimum principles, and foregrounds ethics, community rights, and responsible openness. Recommendations align with UNESCO’s 2003 Convention and its ethical principles, participation and consent requirements, and with professional heritage standards relevant to both tangible and intangible dimensions. The goal is to support living heritage as a dynamic, community-centred process – capable of adaptation, continuity, and contribution to inclusive and sustainable futures.

1 WHY LIVING LABS, WHY NOW

Heritage is increasingly understood not as a static legacy, but as a dynamic process shaped by communities, environments, technologies, and changing social conditions. Conference discussions underscored contemporary forces transforming cultural practice and heritage governance: migration and cultural hybridity, climate impacts and adaptation, evolving identities, and accelerating technological change.

UNESCO’s 2003 Convention established a robust international framework for safeguarding intangible cultural heritage, placing communities at the heart of recognition and safeguarding. At the same time, real-world implementation often faces recurring tensions: expert-driven models may struggle to respond to complexity, to rapid change, and to the lived realities of communities who practise and transmit heritage.

Living labs offer a pragmatic response. Originating in open and user-centred innovation ecosystems, living labs provide structured spaces for collaboration and “learning by doing.” In heritage contexts, they enable communities, institutions, researchers, students, public authorities, and (where appropriate) creative industries to co-design solutions that strengthen continuity, transmission, and responsible innovation.

Digitisation amplifies both opportunities and risks. Digital tools can support community archives, intergenerational transmission, and wider access, but digital fragility (platform instability, format obsolescence, loss of context) threatens long-term memory and accountability. Living labs can help address these tensions by embedding digital work in participatory governance, clear consent processes, and sustainability planning.

In short, heritage living labs are timely because they connect interdisciplinary knowledge, community practice, and innovation in real-world settings – while making ethics and rights operational rather than aspirational.

2 WHAT IS A HERITAGE LIVING LAB?

A Heritage Living Lab is a participatory, real-world environment where safeguarding and sustainable development of cultural heritage are advanced through co-creation, experimentation, and iterative learning. Unlike a conventional laboratory, a heritage living lab operates in situ – within communities, sites, institutions, or hybrid physical-digital environments – and is governed through shared processes rather than expert authority alone.

Scope and roles

A heritage living lab typically:

- Defines a shared challenge or opportunity with the community (not only “for” the community).
- Brings together multiple knowledge systems (local/traditional knowledge, professional practice, academic research, technical expertise).
- Prototypes actions in real conditions (pilots, workshops, demonstrators, seasonal trials).
- Documents outcomes transparently and evaluates them with participants.
- Builds capacity: skills for communities, field experience for students, and participatory competence for institutions.

As open innovation ecosystems, living labs are often described through the quadruple-helix model: civil society (including communities and tradition bearers), academia, public authorities, and the private sector (where relevant) collaborate in structured ways. In heritage settings, this model should be applied carefully: community agency and rights are not “one stakeholder among many,” but a core condition of legitimacy.

Heritage living labs take diverse and often hybrid forms. Many combine different approaches and adapt over time to local contexts and community needs. They may focus on place-based regeneration and stewardship, operate through museums and other institutions as spaces for co-creation and skills transmission, or function as academic and community-anchored settings that support learning and the intergenerational transmission of intangible cultural heritage. Craft-based, circular-economy, and digital or immersive formats often complement in situ practice rather than replace it. Across all forms, what defines a heritage living lab is not its theme or technology, but its governance: shared problem-setting, ethical participation, and learning through practice.

3 CORE PRINCIPLES OF A MINIMUM VIABLE HERITAGE LIVING LAB

A “minimum viable” heritage living lab is not a fully funded institution. It is a credible, ethical, and workable structure that can start small and grow responsibly. The following principles are baseline requirements:

- **Real-world context:** Activities are implemented within authentic community or heritage environments, ensuring that solutions are tested under genuine conditions rather than isolated simulations.
- **Active community participation and agency:** Communities and tradition bearers are not only consulted; they co-define goals, co-create actions, and co-evaluate outcomes.
- **Multidisciplinarity:** Diverse expertise – from craft and humanities to conservation practice, heritage science, and IT – supports shared language and mutual learning.
- **Quadruple-helix collaboration with safeguards:** Public authorities, universities, civic associations, and (where appropriate) private actors participate with clear roles, while protecting community rights and preventing extractive dynamics.
- **Co-creation and iteration:** Solutions evolve through cycles of design, prototyping, feedback, and refinement, enabling adaptive learning.
- **Transparency with consent-aware openness:** Processes and outcomes are documented, but openness is governed: access levels, consent, and cultural sensitivity guide what can be shared, with whom, and how.
- **Integration of conservation and education:** Each lab functions as a learning platform: for communities, professionals, and students, strengthening skills for safeguarding, documentation, and transmission.
- **Shared stewardship of outcomes:** Outcomes are treated as jointly stewarded: tangible products, knowledge outputs, and digital assets have agreed ownership, attribution, and benefit pathways.
- **Monitoring and reflexivity:** The lab includes simple feedback loops: what changed, what worked, what harmed, what should stop, and what should scale.
- **Ethical and inclusive approach:** Respect for cultural diversity, dignity, and rights is non-negotiable, with attention to vulnerable groups and the right to limit dissemination.

4 ETHICS, RIGHTS & OPENNESS

Introducing living labs into heritage practice requires an explicit ethical framework that protects community rights while enabling responsible learning and innovation. Conference discussions highlighted the relevance of several normative instruments and professional principles, including:

- **UNESCO's 2003 Convention for the Safeguarding of Intangible Cultural Heritage** and related guidance emphasising community participation and consent.
- **UNESCO's Ethical Principles for Safeguarding Intangible Cultural Heritage** (endorsed in 2015), placing communities at the heart of safeguarding and calling for free, prior and informed consent.
- **ICOMOS principles** that recognise the interdependence of tangible and intangible dimensions (including “spirit of place”).
- **The ICOM museum definition (2022)** framing museums as participatory, inclusive institutions that work ethically with communities and both tangible and intangible heritage.
- **Relevant WIPO developments on intellectual property**, including the 2024 treaty focused on genetic resources and associated traditional knowledge, and ongoing work related to traditional knowledge and cultural expressions.

5 OPENNESS AND ITS RISKS

Openness – through open data, collaborative archives, participatory documentation, and public engagement – can support transparency, accessibility, and intergenerational transmission. However, openness without governance creates risks:

- **Digital fragility:** Digital heritage can be lost through obsolete formats, platform closures, poor metadata, and lack of institutional stewardship. Sustainability planning is essential from the start (formats, backups, trusted repositories, responsibilities).
- **Commodification:** Excessive adaptation of heritage to external audiences can erode meaning for communities. The guiding question must be: Who benefits, and who carries the costs?
- **Folklorisation:** Folklorisation occurs when living practices are reduced to staged, simplified, or stereotyped representations – often for tourism, branding, or external validation – stripping them of context, complexity, and community control. It can freeze heritage into “performances” of supposed authenticity, discourage natural change, and marginalise the voices of practitioners who do not fit expected narratives. In living labs, folklorisation is a key ethical risk because experimentation and visibility can unintentionally reward the most “marketable” versions of heritage.

Mitigation measures include: community-led interpretation, refusal of forced authenticity criteria, shared decision-making on how practices are presented, benefit-sharing arrangements, and explicit protection of sensitive knowledge.

- **Authorised heritage discourse:** Heritage governance can privilege expert narratives and institutional categories. In a living lab, experts should act as facilitators and translators, not arbiters of legitimacy.
- **Right to withdraw, dignity, and controlled sharing:** Communities must retain the right to limit dissemination of sensitive materials, to correct misrepresentation, and to withdraw from activities that become harmful. Ethical practice includes protecting dignity, privacy, and cultural protocols.

Minimum Ethical Protocol / Living Labs Charter (recommended)

Each Heritage Living Lab should develop an Ethical Protocol or Living Labs Charter, co-authored with participants, covering at minimum:

- Participation design and decision rules (who decides what, and how).
- Free, prior and informed consent procedures (including accessible language and ongoing consent).
- Access levels for outputs (open, restricted, community-only) and culturally appropriate licensing.
- Attribution and acknowledgement standards.
- Data stewardship responsibilities and sustainability plan for digital materials.
- Benefit-sharing principles (financial, reputational, educational, and capacity outcomes).
- Safeguards against commodification and folklorisation.
- Grievance and correction mechanism, including the right to withdraw.

7 EMERGING VISION

The conference concluded with a forward-looking insight: there is no single universal model for heritage living labs. Instead, diverse forms are emerging that complement existing safeguarding approaches.

Site-based labs: These labs are grounded in a specific place, site, or community practice. Their agenda is shaped by local priorities: transmission, community infrastructure, adaptive reuse, or revitalisation of threatened practices. Site-based labs can become part of local cultural ecosystems when co-decision and co-financing models mature, and when municipalities recognise them as legitimate, community-centred cultural infrastructure.

Digital labs: Digital labs operate as online platforms and networks enabling distributed collaboration (including diaspora participation). They may include crowdsourced community archives, participatory documentation, and experimental tools for interpretation. Digital labs can complement site-based labs (for example, as a “digital twin” enabling wider engagement), but they must address inclusivity (digital divide, accessibility) and sustainability (maintenance, stewardship, long-term hosting). Institutional anchoring (libraries, museums, universities) is often decisive for continuity.

Educational labs: Educational labs embed living-lab methods in formal and informal learning: university courses, field schools, professional training, and community workshops. This approach strengthens capacity on all sides: students learn through real challenges, practitioners strengthen participatory skills, and communities gain tangible outputs and documentation that they control and can use. A no-regret step for universities is to embed living lab methodology into curricula, as it provides practical experience for students and tangible results for communities. In a broader sense, this category includes lifelong learning programmes for heritage professionals focused on participation and digital skills.

8 NO-REGRET STEPS FOR PARTNERS

The following measures can be implemented immediately and remain valuable across different funding or policy scenarios:

Establish a Network of Living Heritage Labs

•*Purpose:* connect existing and emerging labs across partners (e.g., within KreativEU and UNESCO UNITWIN networks).

•*Minimum outputs:* a shared contact point, quarterly online exchange, a simple repository of lab descriptions and lessons learned, and an annual peer-learning meeting.

•*Practical value:* reduces duplication, accelerates learning, and supports mentoring for first-wave labs.

Co-develop a Living Labs Charter

•*Purpose:* create a voluntary, shared baseline for ethics and operational standards in heritage living labs.

•*Minimum outputs:* a short charter with agreed principles (participation, consent, controlled openness, benefit-sharing, sustainability, inclusiveness) and a practical checklist.

•*Practical value:* improves trust, clarifies terminology, and makes “ethics” actionable.

Launch Small Pilot Projects (“Quick Wins”)

•*Purpose:* test living-lab practice without waiting for major funding.

•*Minimum outputs:* a small co-creation event, a seasonal pilot, or a limited-scope participatory documentation activity with clear consent and stewardship.

•*Practical value:* reveals real capacities, builds relationships, and generates evidence for scaling.

Connect Creativity and Conservation Responsibly

•*Purpose:* use the living lab as a safe space to explore the relationship between creative interpretation and safeguarding standards.

•*Minimum outputs:* an interdisciplinary prototype (e.g., craft–design collaboration, community storytelling, interpretive intervention) with explicit ethical safeguards.

•*Practical value:* strengthens mutual understanding, prevents polarisation, and can unlock new safeguarding pathways.

Engage Youth and Build “Heritage Futures” Practice

•*Purpose:* support intergenerational continuity by making young people co-creators, not just audiences.

•*Minimum outputs:* youth co-creation formats (summer schools, challenges, apprenticeships, digital

storytelling labs) and a “heritage futures” workshop exploring scenarios of continuity, change, and responsible letting-go.

·*Practical value*: builds skills, agency, and long-term stewardship.

CONCLUSION

Living heritage should not serve only as nostalgia for the past. It is also a resource for shaping sustainable, inclusive futures – when communities can practise, transmit, reinterpret, and adapt heritage on their own terms. Heritage living labs are promising tools for this transformation because they connect safeguarding with learning, innovation, and community empowerment in real contexts.

This Guidance Brief represents a first step: synthesising conference insights into a practical framework while remaining open to refinement through further practice and dialogue. Living heritage is dynamic by definition; heritage living labs must therefore remain flexible, reflexive, and accountable. By following principles of participation, consent, ethical governance, and responsible openness, partners can strengthen heritage as truly living – relevant, creative, and deeply interwoven with everyday life.

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